

THE SENSITISATION SPECTRA OF CERTAIN CYANINE DYES DERIVED FROM α -PICOLINE.

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The sensitiation spectra of the methochloride, the methobromide and the methiodide of 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine have been photographed and the relative sensitising power of these compounds compared.

With a view to examine the influence of change of anion on the properties of cyanine dyes the methochloride, the methobromide and the methiodide of 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine were prepared (Doja, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1940, 17, 347). The relative sensitising power of these dyes for photographic plates has now been examined and reported in this paper. The spectrographs given in Fig. 1 show that the chloride (No. B) does not appreciably increase the range of sensitisation, except a little towards the violet, but enhances the intensity of sensitisation. The

Fig. 1.

A—D refer respectively to unbathed plate, chloride, bromide and iodide

bromide (No. C), in addition to the extra-sensitisation towards the violet, extends the sensitisation on the other side, to about λ 5600 in the green-yellow. The iodide (No. D) maintains the additional sensitisation in the violet, but extends the sensitisation in the yellow still further to about λ 5700.

The photographs were taken on Iiford Process plates. These were bathed for three minutes in solution of the dyestuffs (1:50,000 in rectified spirit), dried by means of an electric fan, and exposed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ minutes to a white light spectrum produced in the following manner :—

FIG. 2.

Light from a 100 c.p. "pointolite" lamp P (Fig. 2) was passed through a lens L, into

the slit (0.12 mm.) of a Hilger's constant deviation wavelength Spectrometer R (glass prism, $n=1.74$), and then allowed to fall on the photographic plate T. In order to render the variation of sensitiveness with wave-length more distinct, a logarithmic sector S, was rotated in front of the slit, by a "Cenco friction drive speed control", at about 60 revolutions per minute. The reference scale

was set up by photographing the helium and mercury lines on the plates with the help of the usual auxiliary comparison prism.

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